

1 [Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies](#)

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40 **Disclaimer**

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51 **Abstract**

52 This protocol describes the design and development of a tool for evaluation of the internal
53 validity of *in vitro* studies, which is needed to include the data as evidence in systematic
54 reviews and chemical risk assessments. The tool will be designed specifically to be applied
55 to cell culture studies, including, but not restricted to studies meeting the new approach
56 methodology (NAM) definition. The tool is called INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies
57 INternal validity).

58 In this protocol, three of the four studies that will be performed to create the release version
59 of INVITES-IN are described. In the first study, evaluation of existing assessment tools will

60 be combined with focus group discussions to identify how characteristics of the design or
61 conduct of an *in vitro* study can affect its internal validity. Bias domains and items considered
62 to be of relevance for *in vitro* studies will be identified. In the second study, group agreement
63 on internal validity domains and items of importance for *in vitro* studies will be identified via a
64 modified Delphi methodology. In the third study, the draft version of the tool will be created,
65 based on the data on relevance and importance of bias domains and items collected in
66 studies one and two. A separate protocol will be prepared for the fourth study, which
67 includes the user testing and validation of the tool, and collection of users' experience.

68 Key words

69 Cell culture, NAMs, Next Generation Risk Assessment, risk of bias.

70 1. Introduction

71 1.1 Evaluation of internal validity

72 This protocol describes the design and development of a tool for evaluation of the internal
73 validity of *in vitro* studies. Internal validity is the extent to which a study (methodological
74 design, methods, and data analysis) is free from bias, where bias is "systematic error, or
75 deviation from the truth, in results" (Cochrane Collaboration, 2005). A test performed *in vitro*
76 ("in the glass") means that it is done outside of a living organism and it usually involves
77 isolated tissues, organs or cells (ECHA, 2023). The tool is called INVITES-IN (IN VITro
78 Experimental Studies INternal validity).

79 Methods to generate evidence for regulatory toxicology are shifting from classical animal
80 experiments to new approach methodologies (NAMs). The European Chemicals Agency and
81 the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency define NAMs as any technology, methodology,
82 approach, or combination that can provide information on chemical hazard and risk
83 assessment without the use of animals, including *in silico*, *in chemico*, *in vitro*, and *ex vivo*
84 approaches (ECHA, 2016; EPA, 2018). According to the European Food Safety Authority
85 (EFSA) the term NAMs is used to make reference to any non-animal-based approach that
86 can be used to provide toxicological information in the context of hazard/risk assessments
87 (EFSA et al., 2022).

88 As part of the gradual incorporation and transition toward the use of NAMs, including *in vitro*
89 studies, a framework for evidence-based use of NAMs in toxicological research and
90 chemical risk assessment is required. Such a framework should ultimately incorporate at
91 least the following principles:

- 92 1. Result in identification of all relevant NAM-generated evidence relating to the
93 research question addressed in a systematic review or risk assessment.
- 94 2. Provide for the evaluation of the internal validity of NAM studies (propensity for
95 systematic error due to how the study is designed and conducted).
- 96 3. Provide for the evaluation of the external validity of NAM studies (the degree to which
97 results of a study can be translated/generalised to human adverse health effects).
- 98 4. Contribute to objectivity, robustness, transparency, and reproducibility in the hazard
99 identification and characterisation process.
- 100 5. In its approach to normalising and structuring the description and analysis of NAMs,
101 contribute to progress in the extent to which research data conforms to FAIR
102 (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) principles of open science.

103 Systematic review and evidence-based toxicology principles should be implemented in all
104 parts of the framework, and it should be generic and usable across different regulatory
105 sectors such as food safety, cosmetic ingredient safety, etc. Principles for incorporating
106 evidence from NAMs into risk assessments and a framework for the evaluation of skin
107 sensitisation have been developed for cosmetic ingredients (Dent et al., 2018; Gilmour et al.,
108 2020). Methods for incorporation of mechanistic studies as supporting evidence in hazard
109 and/or risk assessment is included in the U.S. NTP OHAT handbook for systematic reviews,
110 the ORD staff handbook for developing IRIS assessments, and the draft TSCA interpretation
111 of systematic review methods to support chemical risk evaluations (EPA, 2022; EPA, 2023;
112 NTP OHAT, 2019). However, there is currently no complete framework for evidence-based
113 chemical risk assessment that integrates NAMs to facilitate the transition from use of
114 animals to the use of NAMs in chemical risk assessments.

115 “Next generation risk assessment in practice” is a project in the European Partnership for the
116 Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC). PARC aims to develop next generation
117 chemical risk assessment to advance research, share knowledge and improve skills,
118 protecting human health and the environment. The present project is included in the task
119 focusing on facilitating regulatory acceptance and use of NAMs. PARC is a seven-year
120 partnership under Horizon Europe, including close to 200 institutions from 28 countries
121 working in the areas of the environment or public health, and three EU authorities (PARC,
122 2023). With the “Next generation risk assessment in practice” project, we aim to contribute to
123 the development of a framework for evidence-based use of data generated by *in vitro*
124 studies in human health hazard identification and characterisation by creating tools and
125 guidance’s. A [webpage](#) giving an overview of the planned work in the “Next generation risk
126 assessment in practice” project has been created (VKM, 2023). The first step in our PARC
127 project is to develop a tool for evaluation of internal validity for *in vitro* studies. The next

128 steps, all focusing on *in vitro* studies, will be development of a tool for evaluation of external
129 validity, creation of a guidance for evaluation of certainty in the evidence, and creation of
130 guidance's for the identification of point of departure and the uncertainty in the point of
131 departure. We chose to start focusing on creation of tools for validity assessment, as validity
132 assessment is one of the critical steps in the systematic review process. Further, we chose
133 to start focusing on *in vitro* models as there is a general agreement that these are important
134 as replacement for animal studies to provide information for hazard/risk assessment (ECHA,
135 2016; EFSA et al., 2022; EPA, 2018) in a wider integrating approach. It has been suggested
136 that *in vitro* models could be more suitable than animal models for the prediction of toxicity.
137 For example, *in vitro* data did predict liver toxicity caused by the drug troglitazone whereas
138 neither published animal nor human studies were able to accurately predict the hazard
139 (Dirven et al., 2021).

140 Several *in vitro* study designs exist; however, we have chosen only to focus on cell culture
141 studies (meaning studies using cells derived from multicellular organisms). This delimitation
142 is mainly due to feasibility, especially concerning the user testing, where the number of user
143 testing participants will have to be very large to be able to test that the tool works on all types
144 of *in vitro* study designs.

145 The implementation of this tool might be of help to improve the inclusion of NAMs in the
146 chemical risk assessment process and facilitate regulatory uptake, with a focus on risk
147 assessors' daily practice and workflow.

148 While many tools have been created for assessing *in vitro* studies, there is a priori lack of
149 consensus on developing a tool with the application of rigorous methods. We therefore aim
150 to address this situation by using methods that ensure we are building on prior work, with a
151 degree of rigour consistent with our intent to provide an authoritative assessment tool. We
152 also intend to use the findings of INVITES-IN to prepare a guidance on the design and
153 conduct of *in vitro* studies that will help researchers minimise and/or transparently identify
154 potential biases in their studies.

155 1.2 Objective

156 The aim of this project is to create INVITES-IN, a tool for evaluating the internal validity of *in*
157 *vitro* studies. The INVITES-IN tool will be designed specifically to be applied to cell culture
158 models (e.g. cell lines, primary cell models, co-cultures, monolayer and 3-D cell models
159 systems) treated with a single-chemical substance exposure, measuring any outcome We
160 anticipate that the tool will be applicable (potentially with modification) to other *in vitro* study

161 designs or other NAMs such as organ-on-a-chip, *in ovo*, *fish embryos*, *ex vivo*, *in chemico*,
162 etc, and chemical mixture studies, but this will not be addressed in this study.

163 To contribute to its usability, INVITES-IN will be accompanied by instructions to guide the
164 user through the evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies step-by-step. While there is
165 good empirical evidence from several domains that certain features of how a study is
166 designed, conducted, and analysed can introduce bias, it is usually not possible to determine
167 how much bias a given feature has introduced on any specific occasion (Savović et al.,
168 2012). INVITES-IN therefore follows conventional guidance (Boutron et al., 2022; Frampton
169 et al., 2022) in being designed to differentiate studies with relatively higher risk of bias from
170 studies with relatively lower risk of bias.

171 1.3 Project governance

172 The development of INVITES-IN is part of the PARC project “Next generation risk
173 assessment in practice” [Project 101057014 – [PARC](#)]. A project group (PG) has been
174 established with the responsibility for developing and implementing the tool for evaluation of
175 internal validity of *in vitro* studies. The project is led by the Norwegian Institute of Public
176 Health represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment
177 (Norway). The project partners are Benaki Phytopathological Institute (Greece), Istituto
178 Superiore di Sanità (Italy) and the University of Basel (Switzerland).

179 A scientific advisory group (SAG) consisting of experts in systematic review principles,
180 chemical risk assessment, toxicology, NAMs, and/or methods for tool development, several
181 of whom have been directly involved in developing approaches to assessing the validity of *in*
182 *vitro* studies, has been established. The SAG gives strategic guidance and support to the
183 PG and share information about ongoing projects addressing similar questions to ensure
184 that the outcome of this project complements and builds on the work of others and thereby
185 creates synergies and avoids duplication of efforts.

186 2 Materials and methods

187 2.1 Study design

188 2.1.1 An overview of the creation of INVITES-IN

189 The method for creating INVITES-IN will follow the general framework for developing quality
190 assessment tools suggested by Whiting et al. (2017). This is a broad framework of general
191 principles rather than a tightly-prescribed standard but gives the general structure of our
192 approach. Four studies will be performed to create INVITES-IN (Figure 1). This protocol
193 describes Studies 1, 2 and 3, and the timeline is shown in Figure 2. A separate protocol will
194 be prepared for Study 4.

195 The tool will consist of signalling questions and criteria for reaching risk-of-bias judgments
 196 for each signalling question. Criteria are the issues that have to be fulfilled to avoid bias.
 197 Signalling questions are questions that the users of the tool answer in order to determine
 198 whether the criteria have been fulfilled. The technical solution for the tool has not yet been
 199 decided; however, we intend to make an online tool.

200

201 **Figure 1.** An overview of the four studies that will be performed to create the release version
 202 of INVITES- IN.

203

204

205

206 **Figure 2.** An overview of the 2023/24 timeline for the creation of the beta version of
 207 INVITES-IN.

208 The target group for the use of the tool (i.e., end-users) includes *in vitro* scientists and risk
 209 assessors conducting literature reviews in hazard assessments/safety evaluations, which

210 could be part of a chemical risk/safety assessment, a systematic review or both, for
211 regulatory or research purposes.

212 To get the input we need to develop the tool, we aim to recruit participants experienced with
213 *in vitro* research that are representative for the end-users. For the studies 1 and 3, we aim to
214 recruit some participants also having experience with systematic reviews, some also having
215 experience with chemical risk assessment, and some having no experience with systematic
216 reviews or chemical risk assessments. For study 2, we consider it critical that all participants
217 have systematic review experience, as this is the study where the importance of different
218 internal validity items will be ranked. Previous experience with evaluation of internal validity
219 is considered important to be able to rank importance of different internal validity items. All
220 groups of end-expected users are covered by the networks of the PG and the SAG. Potential
221 participants will therefore be identified through nomination by PG and SAG members, who
222 will be requested to nominate three potential participants. For each nominated participant, an
223 overview of their scientific expertise and experience, affiliation, geographical location, and
224 gender will be prepared. From the pool of nominated participants, PG will select participants
225 that will be invited. In the selection process, PG will ensure diversity among the participants
226 by including scientists from different fields having different professional backgrounds and
227 experience with different cell culture models, covering a variety of geographical locations,
228 and having an even gender distribution. In each focus group, all participants should be
229 affiliated with different institutions, located in at least four different countries. This way we will
230 avoid having an overrepresentation of focus group participants from a few institutions or from
231 a too limited number of countries. We consider that this described process will make it
232 possible to carry out the recruitment without it being an overly time-consuming process, and
233 at the same time secure sufficient diversity in the group of participants.

234 The tasks and workload for the participants, the outcome of their contribution, and the
235 participant eligibility criteria, are shown in Figure 3 and Table 1. Note that it is not expected
236 that the same persons participate in all studies. It is planned that the persons participating in
237 Study 1 will be also invited to participate in Study 3.

238 For all three studies, the potential participants will receive information about the project when
239 they are contacted by email, and participants that accept the invitation will be requested to
240 complete a declaration of interest form. The PG will evaluate the declaration of interest
241 forms, focusing mainly on identification of potential conflicts of interest that may interfere with
242 the participants contribution and role in the focus group discussion.

243 Previous studies report average or median time for the assessment of RoB of a study to
244 range from 20 to 40 minutes (Eick et al., 2020; Momen et al., 2022). We intend to keep the
245 time needed for assessment of one cell culture study within this range.

246 All data analyses will be done by the PG members. All raw data from each study will be
247 anonymised and made available as supplementary to the respective publications.

248

Study 1 Focus group discussions	18-24 participants (12 is the minimum).
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• All participate in two online focus group discussions (~90 min for each discussion).• Three focus groups in total (two is the minimum; six to eight participants per group).• A PG member leads the discussion. <p><u>Outcome</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Items and criteria relevant for <i>in vitro</i> studies are identified.• Items of no/low relevance for <i>in vitro</i> studies are eliminated.	
Study 2 Delphi survey	20-30 participants (15 is the minimum).
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• All complete two online surveys (~4 h).• At least 10 participate in the online guided discussion (~60 min).• A PG member leads the guided discussion. <p><u>Outcome</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Items and criteria important for introduction of bias to <i>in vitro</i> studies are identified.• Items considered to be of low/no importance are eliminated.	
Study 3 Workshops	5-24 participants.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The participants from study 1 will be invited.• All participate in one online workshop (~60 min).• A PG member leads the workshop. <p><u>Outcome</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strengths and weaknesses of the guidance document are identified.• Feedback and suggestions for revisions are received.	

249

250 **Figure 3.** Participants' tasks and workload in Study 1 to 3, and the outcome of their
251 contribution.

252

253 **Table 1.** An overview of the criteria for participation in Study 1 to 3.

Selection of participants		Study 1	Study 2	Study 3
Scientific experience and expertise	<i>In vitro</i> models	x		x
	<i>In vitro</i> models AND chemical risk assessment	x		x
	<i>In vitro</i> models AND systematic review methods	x	x	x
	<i>In vitro</i> models AND experienced with the development of relevant guidance documents for chemical risk assessors	x		x
Balancing factors	Academia	x	x	x
	Governmental institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes)	x	x	x
	Private sector research institutions	x	x	x
	Gender distribution	x	x	x
	Demographic distribution	x	x	x
	Regional distribution	x	x	x
Academic level	Post-doctoral level or higher	x	x	x
Language	English, level B1 or higher	x	x	x

254

255 2.1.2 Ethical review

256 Ethical approval has been given by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

257 2.2 Study 1: Creating the alpha version of the tool

258 2.2.1 Introduction and objective

259 The objective of Study 1 is to create a straw-man or alpha version of INVITES-IN that can be
260 further developed via a modified Delphi process (see section 2.3.2 for description). In Study
261 1, a list of characteristics of the design, conduct, and analysis of an *in vitro* study that can
262 introduce bias into its results or findings will be compiled, organised thematically, and then
263 interpreted into a draft set of structured signalling questions that constitute the alpha version
264 of INVITES-IN.

265 The knowledge goal is to have the expert interpretations of the relevance of bias domains
266 and items for *in vitro* studies.

267 A pilot focus group discussion was arranged to get an impression of the time needed for the
 268 focus group discussions, to test the technical functions, and to get feedback on factors
 269 related to the presentation of questions and the use of examples that may be of importance
 270 to conduct successful focus group discussions.

271 **2.2.2 Method**

272 We will include three focus groups with six to eight participants in each group (Figure 3).

273 An overview of the workflow and the responsibilities in Study 1 are given Table 2.

274 **Table 2.** An overview of Study 1.

Phase	Task	Responsible
Plan	Prepare the list of bias domains and items.	Project group
	Create questions for the focus group discussions.	
	Define inclusion criteria for focus group participants.	Project group and scientific advisory group
	Nominate and recruit focus group participants fulfilling the inclusion criteria.	
Actions	Carry out the focus group discussions.	Project group
	Analyse results and prepare the final report.	
Result	Bias domains and items of relevance for <i>in vitro</i> studies are identified and included in the alpha version of the tool.	Project group

275

276 **2.2.2.1 Identifying relevant bias domains and items**

277 A list of bias domains and items of potential relevance for *in vitro* studies will be prepared
 278 using several literature sources. This list will serve as a starting point for the creation of
 279 INVITES-IN and provide the basis for the focus group discussions. The literature sources are
 280 as follows: two systematic reviews on validity tools for *in vitro* models (Tran et al., 2021;
 281 Whaley et al., in preparation), a publication on study sensitivity that includes assessment
 282 items that may relate to internal validity but may not be included in other tools (Cooper et al.,
 283 2016), and tools for evaluation of risk of bias (EPA, 2022; NTP OHAT, 2015; NTP OHAT,
 284 2019; Roth et al., 2021; Sterne et al., 2019).

285 **2.2.2.2 Focus group participants**

286 Eligible focus group participants will be scientists with or without systematic review
 287 experience that are active in the field of *in vitro* research in academia, governmental
 288 institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or private research
 289 institutes, at post-doctoral level or higher, and level B1 English speakers (see Table 1). PG

290 and SAG will nominate participants. We aim to have an equal gender distribution, a
291 reasonable demographic and regional distribution, and a group size of six to eight
292 participants as this group size is recommended to generate diverse ideas but not so many
293 participants that they do not have a chance to share perspectives (Krueger et al., 2001). The
294 minimum number of participants in a focus group is considered to be four. All participants in
295 a focus group will be affiliated with different institutions in an attempt to achieve variation in
296 input and perspective, and they should be working with a variety of *in vitro* models to cover a
297 wide range of experimental systems. No compensation is offered for the participation, and
298 participants will not be offered co-authorship.

299 Potential focus group participants will be contacted via email. They will receive a document
300 with information about the project, the purpose of the focus groups and the focus group
301 discussions, that the use of information learned in the meeting will not allow for identification
302 of the focus group participants, the withdrawal procedure, the financial source, and the
303 approximate time for the focus group meeting. Focus group participants must actively
304 confirm their consent by email.

305 We aim to have three different focus groups (Krueger et al., 2001), however, two groups are
306 considered to be the minimum. All groups will be presented with the same information and
307 questions, although the direction in which discussion is steered may depend on how
308 comprehensively previous focus groups were able to cover each issue. The need for
309 including an additional group will be discussed if new insights are presented during the
310 meetings, or if areas needing discussion were not addressed.

311 *2.2.2.3 Focus group discussion*

312 We plan to have two group discussions per focus group. The second meeting will be
313 cancelled if considered not to be needed. The discussions will be carried out as online
314 meetings and will be recorded. A PG member will act as a focus group moderator and lead
315 the discussions in the meeting, and another PG member will handle the logistics (the
316 assistant moderator).

317 The complete list of identified bias domains and items will be the starting point for the focus
318 group discussions. The discussions will be facilitated with a view to addressing two
319 questions (numbering is for referencing purposes and the questions will not necessarily be
320 presented in this order):

- 321 1. Are there any gaps in the identified domains or items that could influence systematic
322 error in an *in vitro* study?
- 323 2. What characteristics of the design, conduct, or analysis of an *in vitro* study could
324 introduce systematic error into its results or findings?

325 Question (1) will be addressed both by asking directly and inferred from analysis of the
 326 discussion (see section 2.2.2.4 below). Question (2) will be directly asked.

327 Discussion relating to questions (1) and (2) will be structured in terms of the bias domains
 328 defined in the Scientific Evidence Code System ([SEVCO](#)) (Table 3) (Alper et al., 2021b). The
 329 SEVCO domains are chosen because they are consistent with the bias domains of Whaley
 330 et al. (in prep) and the OHAT tool (NTP OHAT, 2019) but represent a more recent
 331 normalised list of bias categories derived from a robust grounding and consensus process
 332 (Alper et al., 2021a). These definitions are developed for human studies, and the relevance
 333 for *in vitro* studies will be discussed in the focus groups. We acknowledge that not all bias
 334 domains presented in Table 3 may be of relevance for *in vitro* studies. However, we will
 335 include all bias domains with approved SEVCO definitions in the focus group discussions in
 336 order to collect expert feedback on the relevance for *in vitro* studies. SEVCO draft bias
 337 domains that have not been approved are not listed. Participants may suggest additional
 338 bias domains.

339 **Table 3.** Bias domains with approved definitions in the Scientific Evidence Code System
 340 (FEvIR Platform Version 0.80.0, 06.12.2022).

Bias Domain	Definition	SEVCO code reference
Selection Bias	A bias resulting from methods used to select subjects or data, factors that influence initial study participation, or differences between the study sample and the population of interest	SEVCO:00002
Confounding Covariate Bias	A situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable. For confounding covariate bias to occur the distorting variable must be (1) associated with the exposure and the outcome, (2) not in the causal pathway between exposure and outcome, and (3) unequally distributed between the groups being compared.	SEVCO:00016
Performance Bias	A bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure	SEVCO:00017
Attrition Bias	A bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.	SEVCO:00019

Detection Bias	A bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable.	SEVCO:00020
Analysis Bias	A bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.	SEVCO:00021
Reporting Bias	A bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings.	SEVCO:00023
Early Study Termination Bias	A bias due to the decision to end the study earlier than planned.	SEVCO:00370

341

342 Focus group participants will be shown and have read to them the definitions for each bias
343 domain. Participants will then be led in discussion of how the domain might be active in the
344 *in vitro* context, with examples from their practical research experience of how systematic
345 error can be introduced into an *in vitro* study. For each bias domain, one example for animal
346 studies and one example for *in vitro* studies will be prepared and these will be presented
347 when there is a need for further clarification to start the discussion.

348 Participants will be given an option to send additional thoughts and considerations on the
349 relevance of the discussed bias domains and items for *in vitro* studies to the PG by email
350 within a week after the focus group discussion.

351 *2.2.2.4 Data analysis and reporting*

352 Focus group transcripts will be analysed for potential risk of bias criteria and items that could
353 be added to the alpha version of INVITES-IN. For time efficiency, transcripts of the focus
354 group discussions will be machine-generated. Errors in transcription will only be corrected
355 when they affect coding and interpretation of the discussion and will be done by the focus
356 group moderator and the assistant moderator. Anonymised transcripts will be shared as raw
357 data and be included as supplementary materials. The original recordings, as they contain
358 personally identifiable information, will not be made available.

359 The focus group transcripts will be annotated (coded) in order to provide qualitative data on
360 the following: preferences of the participants for traditional versus more recent approaches
361 to structure risk of bias assessment (“preferred approach”), including reasons for and
362 against; the participants’ ideas about how researchers’ approaches to designing, conducting,
363 analysing and reporting studies (“issues”) can potentially introduce systematic error,
364 including their potential importance; the participants ideas about when (“time-point”)

365 systematic error is introduced; the participants ideas about the relevance (“relevance”) for *in*
 366 *vitro* studies.

367 Data on preferred approach, issues, time-points, and relevance will be annotated by two
 368 investigators with a high level of expertise in bias assessment working independently then
 369 reconciling their coding decisions in discussion with a third investigator with experience in
 370 coding and reconciliation. The annotation environment will be Microsoft Word. The
 371 annotators will reach consensus for coding using the codebook through coding a part of one
 372 transcript together and discussing differences in interpretation, and they will agree on the
 373 rules for annotation (e.g., sentence or word highlighting for codes) and document these as
 374 their coding strategy in a coding manual.

375 Coding will be a mix of deductive (prespecified) and inductive (ad hoc) annotation. The
 376 definitions of the deductive codes are included in Table 4. , and we have also indicated
 377 where we already anticipate that codes will be developed inductively, though further
 378 inductive codes will be developed as needed. The Code Book is shown in Table 5. A report
 379 of the results of the annotation exercise, as a set of excerpted text strings aggregated under
 380 code categories and labelled with specific codes, will be generated as data for supporting
 381 development of the alpha version of INVITES-IN.

382 **Table 4.** The definition of the codes in the Code Book.

Code Category	Code	Definition
Issue	- Selection	An issue relating to selection bias
	- Confounding	An issue relating to confounding covariates bias
	- Performance	An issue relating to performance bias
	- Attrition	An issue relating to attrition bias
	- Detection	An issue relating to detection bias
	- Analysis	An issue relating to analysis bias
	- Reporting	An issue relating to reporting bias
	- Early Termination	An issue relating to early termination bias
	- [ad hoc codes]	Ad hoc codes will be created to classify limitations that do not fit into any of the prespecified bias categories (inductive coding)
Time-point	- Before exposure	An issue that may affect potential for systematic error prior to the exposure (administration of the chemical substance) in the experiment

	- During exposure	An issue that may affect potential for systematic error during the exposure (administration of the chemical substance) in the experiment
	- After exposure	An issue that may affect potential for systematic error after the exposure (administration of the chemical substance) in the experiment
Relevance	- Higher relevance	Argument or observation that an issue that may affect potential for systematic error is of potentially higher relevance
	- Lower relevance	Argument or observation that an issue that may affect potential for systematic error is of potentially lower relevance

383

384 **Table 5.** The Code Book.

Level 1	Level 2
Selection	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Confounding	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Performance	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Attrition	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance

- Detection	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Analysis	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Reporting	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- Early Termination	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance
- [ad hoc codes]	- Before exposure
	- During exposure
	- After exposure
	- Higher relevance
	- Lower relevance

385

386 2.2.3 Results and outcome

387 The focus group participants will not make decisions but provide ideas and
388 recommendations. Their feedback on issues, time-points, and relevance for the *in vitro*
389 context will be used by the PG to prepare the alpha version of INVITES-IN, which will
390 contain all bias domains and items considered to be of relevance for *in vitro* studies with
391 reasonings. The final decisions regarding the inclusion of bias domains and items in the
392 alpha version of INVITES-IN will be made by the PG members involved in this study. An
393 overview of bias domains and items that are not included in the alpha version will be
394 included in the study report, and comprehensively documented in supporting data. The intent
395 here is not to permanently exclude any items, but to generate a list of practical length for

396 analysis by the modified Delphi process. Decisions about exclusion of domains or items at
397 this stage affect only the alpha version of INVITES-IN and are not final: if the Delphi process
398 reintroduces any excluded concepts, this will supersede the initial decision made by the PG.

399 2.3 Study 2: Determining bias domains and items of importance for *in vitro* studies

400 2.3.1 Introduction and objective

401 The objective is to eliminate, add to, or refine the proposed bias domains and assessment
402 items that are generated by Study 1. This provides the final data to be interpreted into the
403 beta version of INVITES-IN in Study 3.

404 The feature tested is the importance of the bias domains and items included in the alpha
405 version of INVITES-IN for the internal validity of *in vitro* studies.

406 The knowledge goal is to have the expert interpretations of the importance of bias domains
407 and items for *in vitro* studies.

408 2.3.2 Method

409 A modification of the Delphi technique (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963) will be used to obtain
410 subjective opinions on the importance of bias domains and items for *in vitro* studies from
411 experts experienced with both *in vitro* studies and systematic review principles. The Delphi
412 technique gives the opportunity to collect subjective expert statements anonymously and
413 gives the desired transparency, without e.g. social or personality-based factors resulting in
414 one expert's feedback influencing the feedback another expert in the group. Therefore, this
415 approach is considered to be an appropriate technique to identify expert agreement.

416 A two-round digital Delphi survey will be conducted, followed by an online workshop for
417 guided discussions. In both rounds, expert panellists will complete a questionnaire. From
418 each Delphi round, the outcome will be subjective expert feedback on importance of bias
419 domains and items, and we will use these data to identify expert agreement on bias domains
420 and items important for internal validity of *in vitro* studies. Bias domains and items for which
421 agreement were not reached during the two Delphi rounds will be discussed in the
422 workshop. In addition, the participants will be asked to give input on the wording of the
423 questions in each Delphi round and during the guided discussion.

424 An overview of the workflow and the responsibilities in Study 2 is given Table 6.

425 **Table 6.** An overview of Study 2.

Phase	Task	Responsible
Plan	Define inclusion criteria for Delphi participants (expert panellists).	Project group

	Nominate and recruit expert panellists fulfilling the inclusion criteria.	Project group and scientific advisory group
	Create the questionnaire addressing the bias domains and items relevant for <i>in vitro</i> studies identified in Study 1.	
Actions	<u>Delphi round 1</u> Expert panellists complete the questionnaire and have the possibility to suggest additional bias domains and items.	Project group
	<u>Between Delphi round 1 and 2</u> Analyse results from round 1. Feedback from round 1 is given to the expert panellists. Bias domains and items which met criteria for identification of agreement for inclusion in INVITES-IN are removed. Bias domains and items which met criteria for identification of agreement for exclusion from INVITES-IN are removed. New questions may be included, existing questions may be revised.	
	<u>Delphi round 2</u> Feedback from round 1 is given to the expert panellists. Expert panellists complete the questionnaire. Analyse results from round 2.	
	<u>Workshop</u> Expert panellists will be guided through a discussion of uncertainties related to bias domains and items for which agreement for inclusion or exclusion were not identified. Prepare transcripts, organise, and summarise results.	Project group
Result	Expert agreement on bias domains and items of importance for internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> studies is identified.	Project group

426

427 [2.3.2.1 Delphi participants](#)

428 Eligible Delphi participants will be scientists that are active in the field of *in vitro* research and
429 have some experience with systematic literature review principles, are affiliated in academia,

430 governmental institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or
431 private research institutes, at post-doctoral level or higher, and level B1 English speakers
432 (see Table 1). PG and SAG will nominate participants.

433 We aim to have an even gender and geographical location distribution for the potential
434 participants that are invited to participate. The number of participants will be 20 to 30 (see
435 Figure 3), depending on the number of suitable candidates identified by PG and SAG and
436 the candidate's willingness to participate. The minimum number of participants is considered
437 to be 15.

438 Potential participants will be contacted via email, and they will receive a letter with
439 information about the project and the purpose of the Delphi survey including the fact that the
440 use of individual survey responses will not allow for identification of the participant, the
441 withdrawal procedure, the financial source, as well as the approximate time for completion of
442 the questionnaires. Participants must actively confirm their consent by email to be included
443 as a participant. Before each Delphi round and the guided discussion, participants will
444 receive instructions. Participants are eligible to be co-authors of the Delphi study manuscript
445 if they also read and comment on the final draft. No compensation or other incentives are
446 offered for the participation.

447 *2.3.2.2 Delphi rounds and workshop with guided discussion*

448 A Delphi round is defined as the process where the expert panellists complete a
449 questionnaire. Before each round, expert panellists will receive a document with information
450 about the project, the Delphi survey, and how the Delphi questionnaire information will be
451 handled and used.

452 The PG develops the questionnaire based on the alpha version of INVITES-IN prepared in
453 Study 1. The questionnaire will be prepared as an Excel form, and it will be sent to the
454 expert panellists by email. The expert panellists rate the importance of different bias
455 domains and items for the internal validity of *in vitro* studies. A 5-point Likert scale, with the
456 categories "strongly disagree" (1), moderately disagree (2), neutral (3), moderately agree (4),
457 and strongly agree (5) is used as response options (Verhagen et al., 1998).

458 The expert panellists will have two weeks to complete the questionnaire in each Delphi
459 round, and they will receive up to three email reminders to complete each round. Panellists
460 not responding within the deadline in one of the two Delphi rounds will be excluded from that
461 round. Removed participants will not be replaced. Participants excluded from the first round
462 will also be excluded from the second round.

463 **Delphi round 1:** The questionnaire is completed by the expert panellists, and they will also
464 be able to suggest additional bias domains and items and alternative wording.

465 **Between Delphi round one and two:**

- 466 - The results are analysed, and expert panellists receive feedback on average rating
467 and distribution of ratings of importance of bias domain and items.
- 468 - The questionnaire is revised. Bias domains and items which met criteria for
469 identification of agreement for inclusion or exclusion from INVITES-IN are removed.
470 New questions may be included, existing questions may be revised.

471 **Delphi round 2:** The revised questionnaire is completed by the expert panellists.

472 **Between Delphi round two and the workshop:**

- 473 - Results are analysed, and expert panellists receive feedback on average rating and
474 distribution of ratings of importance of bias domain and items.
- 475 - Bias domains and items that did not reach agreement for either inclusion or exclusion
476 in round two are included in the guided discussion workshop. An overview of all bias
477 domains and items that did not reach agreement for either inclusion or exclusion will
478 be prepared and sent to the expert panellists who will be requested to include
479 arguments for considering the items to be of higher or lower importance. PG will
480 prepare an overview of all arguments, which will be sent to workshop participants.

481 **Workshop:** A workshop will be arranged to have a guided discussion on items where no
482 agreement on importance for *in vitro* studies has been identified. The starting point for the
483 discussion of each of these items will be the overview of arguments created between the
484 Delphi round two and the workshop. During the discussion, we will ask the participants to
485 give reasonings for agreeing or disagreeing with the arguments. New arguments that
486 emerge from the guided discussion will be included in the overview. A PG member will lead
487 and moderate the guided discussion. The workshop will be recorded and transcripts from the
488 workshop will form the basis for the revision of the list of arguments.

489 *2.3.2.3 Data analysis and reporting*

490 One PG member will send out the questionnaires, receive the completed questionnaires
491 from the expert panellists, and anonymise the answers. This person will not be involved in
492 the data analysis.

493 Expert panellist characteristics such as gender distribution and geographic localisation will
494 be reported. The response rate (percentage) for expert panellist completing the Delphi
495 survey will be calculated and reported. The average group response, changes in rating

496 between rounds, as well as modifications of the questionnaire, will be reported. The expert
497 panellists rating of the questions will be analysed independently for round one, round two,
498 and the guided discussion, and median, mean, standard deviation and the interquartile
499 range will be reported.

500 Criteria for identification of agreement in round one and two:

- 501 - Agreement for inclusion of bias domains and items is identified when 70% of the
502 expert panellists rate the relevance and wording of a question as the category
503 “moderately agree” or “strongly agree” (1 and 2 on the 5-point Likert scale).
- 504 - Agreement for exclusion of bias domains and items is identified when 70% of the
505 expert panellists rate the relevance of a question as the category “moderately
506 disagree” or “strongly disagree” (1 and 2 on the 5-point Likert scale).

507 Decisions on identification of agreement will be made by the PG members involved in this
508 study.

509 The transcripts from the workshop will be anonymised and made available as supplementary
510 materials.

511 2.3.3 Results and outcome

512 Study 2 will result in a list of bias domains and items i) for which there were agreement that
513 the domain or item is of importance when evaluating risk of bias of *in vitro* studies, ii) for
514 which there were agreement that the domain or item is not of importance when evaluating
515 risk of bias of *in vitro* studies, and iii) where agreement was not reached for either inclusion
516 or exclusion in the two rounds of Delphi or in the guided discussion. For the items where
517 agreement was not reached, arguments for considering a given item as higher or lower
518 importance will be included.

519 2.4 Study 3: Creating the beta version of INVITES-IN

520 2.4.1 Introduction and objective

521 The objective is to create the beta version of INVITES-IN, that will be advanced to user
522 testing. This will consist of two elements: the tool itself, consisting of a set of signalling
523 questions and a process for deriving a risk of bias assessment; and a guidance document
524 explaining how to use the tool. The guidance document will also include relevant examples
525 of ratings of cell culture studies. This will be given as short texts illustrating possible
526 reporting in a publication together with explanations and reasonings for how this is intended
527 to be rated when applying INVITES-IN.

528 The knowledge goal is to have a complete set of signalling questions addressing bias
 529 domains and items of importance for introduction of bias to *in vitro* studies and the criteria for
 530 the rating of the questions.

531 **2.4.2 Method**

532 An overview of the workflow and the responsibilities in Study 3 is shown in Table 7.

533 **Table 7.** An overview of Study 3.

Phase	Task	Responsible
Plan	Signalling questions are formulated. Guidance for rating the signalling questions is prepared. The process for compiling the results from the rating of the signalling questions into an overall assessment of the risk of bias for each study is created.	Project group
	Invite members of the focus group that interpreted bias domains and items for <i>in vitro</i> context (Study 1) to participate in an online workshop.	
Actions	<u>Workshop</u> Get feedback on the presentation of and information in the guidance document (Study 1).	Project group
Result	The guidance is revised according to the workshop feedback. The beta version of INVITES-IN is finalised.	Project group

534

535 **2.4.2.1 Draft version of INVITES-IN**

536 The draft version of INVITES-IN will be prepared by the PG. The outcome of Study 2 will be
 537 used to formulate the signalling questions. The guidance document will contain explanations
 538 of how each signalling question should be rated.

539 **2.4.2.2 Workshop participants**

540 Members of the focus group participating in Study 1 will be invited to participate in an online
 541 workshop, except for those who also participated in the Delphi process which will be
 542 excluded. No compensation is offered for participation, and participants will not be offered
 543 co-authorship.

544 **2.4.2.3 Workshops**

545 One or more online workshops will be arranged to collect feedback on both the presentation
 546 and the information in the guidance document. Regarding the feedback on information in the
 547 guidance document, the focus will be on the suggested criteria for the rating of the signalling

548 questions and whether we have succeeded in formulating these so that it is the factors that
549 are of considered to be of greatest importance for the introduction of bias that are given the
550 most weight.

551 We also attempt to collect feedback from the participants regarding the presentation of the
552 signalling questions from the workshops; whether they should be structured according to the
553 relevant bias domains or be based on study characteristics and structured around whether
554 the bias is introduced before, during or after the exposure of the experimental system to the
555 test item (i.e. prior, during and after the administration of the chemical substance in the
556 experiment).

557 When possible, the number of participants in a workshop will be six to eight. However,
558 workshops with fewer participants will be considered in order to facilitate participant
559 recruitment. The workshops will be recorded.

560 *2.4.2.4 Data analysis and reporting*

561 Transcripts of the feedback on the guidance document received in the workshops will be
562 prepared and made available as supplementary materials. Based on the feedback from
563 participants in the workshops, PG will make the final decision on the need for revision.

564 *2.4.3 Results and outcome*

565 The beta version of the tool is ready for user testing.

566 *3 Discussion*

567 This protocol describes the methodological approach for the development of the INVITES-IN
568 tool. . In this protocol, we have proposed an approach similar to that of ROB2 (Sterne et al.,
569 2019) and ROBINS (Sterne et al., 2016). The approach chosen fulfils the framework for
570 developing quality assessment tools (Whiting et al., 2017), which is to our knowledge the
571 only existing framework for how to develop quality appraisal tools. Although, we cannot be
572 certain that the chosen approach is the best approach, we feel confident that the methods
573 chosen are rigorous and have been agreed upon of more than 20 experienced
574 experts/scientists. Also, we have focused on transparency and there detailed method
575 descriptions and collected data (transcripts and more) will be made publicly available. Our
576 methodological approach comprises four separate studies and involves both focus groups,
577 two-round Delphi survey and user-testing at different stages. A separate protocol will be
578 prepared for the user testing (Study 4). Involving groups of experts in every study reduces
579 the level of expert judgements made by the project group and also ensure that the tool
580 development is based on a wide range of feedback from experts that are the intended user
581 of the tool. It might be that including more participants in the three studies described in this

582 protocol would give additional interpretations of the relevance and importance of bias
583 domains and items for *in vitro* studies. It may be a challenge to recruit enough experts to
584 ensure sufficiently powering of the studies. To facilitate the recruitment process, the
585 workload for the participants is limited to the absolute minimum. Also, participants in the
586 Delphi-survey, which are likely to have the largest workload for the participants, will be
587 offered authorship on the Delphi study manuscript.

588 The described approach will not include the assessment of magnitude or direction of the
589 bias. We believe that these issues need to be addressed by empirical research in addition to
590 expert knowledge elicitation. We acknowledge the importance of assessing magnitude and
591 the direction of bias, however, the amount of work and time it will take to properly address
592 this, will not be possible at this stage of the tool development.

593 Given that assessment of *in vitro* studies is likely to become a fast-moving field, we
594 acknowledge there may be a need for the tool to be updated to reflect rapid changes in
595 consensus on how to do this, and/or it may be fast movement toward modifying INVITES-IN
596 for other specific NAM study designs. A plan for the update or modification of INVITES-IN is
597 not included in this protocol, as it is restricted to describe the process for the creation of this
598 tool.

599 [Dissemination](#)

600 A focus group interview report will be prepared.

601 A Delphi process report will be prepared, including the questionnaires used in round one and
602 round two.

603 The beta version of the tool, ready for user testing, will be prepared.

604 [Abbreviations](#)

605 NAM: new approach methodologies

606 PG: project group

607 SAG: scientific advisory group

608 [Definitions](#)

609 **Bias** are systematic errors, or deviations from the truth, in results or inference (Cochrane
610 Collaboration, 2005). For *in vitro* studies, systematic errors may be introduced in the study
611 design, conduction, and/or analysis, and cause the result to be an overestimate or
612 underestimate.

613 **Bias domains** are themes such as study performance, analysis, and reporting, under which
614 bias items can be organised/grouped.

615 **Bias items** are study properties that may be relevant for introduction of bias in results and/or
616 their interpretation. Criteria are the issues that have to be fulfilled for bias to be avoided. In
617 the guidance document for the INVITES-IN tool there will be criteria for reaching risk-of-bias
618 judgements for each signalling question.

619 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have
620 prevented bias (Cochrane Collaboration, 2005).

621 **In vitro** ("in the glass") tests means that it is done outside of a living organism and it usually
622 involves isolated tissues, organs or cells (ECHA, 2023).

623 **NAMs** have not yet a standard definition. However, there seems to be a general agreement
624 that the term "NAMs" include *in chemico*, *in silico* and *in vitro* studies. One established
625 definition is that NAMS includes any technology, methodology, approach, or combination
626 that can provide information on chemical hazard and risk assessment without the use of
627 animals, including *in silico*, *in chemico*, *in vitro*, and *ex vivo* approaches (ECHA, 2016; EPA,
628 2018).

629 **Risk of bias** are a measure for systematic errors. Risk of bias tools are used for evaluation
630 of the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have prevented bias
631 (the degree of systematic errors).

632 **Signalling questions** are the questions that the users of the tool answer in order to
633 determine whether the criteria have been fulfilled.

634 **Validity** is the degree to which a result (of a measurement or study) is likely to be true and
635 free of bias (systematic errors) (Cochrane Collaboration, 2005).

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644 Ethical approval has been given by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

645 [Declaration of interests](#)

646 Completed declaration of interest forms for each author are available as supplementary
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666 Mathisen.

667 [References](#)

668 Alper B.S., Dehnbostel J., Afzal M., Subbian V., Soares A., Kunnamo I., Shahin K., McClure
669 R.C. (2021a) Making science computable: Developing code systems for statistics,
670 study design, and risk of bias. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics* 115:103685. DOI:
671 10.1016/j.jbi.2021.103685.

672 Alper B.S., Dehnbostel J., Lehmann H., Whaley P., Wilkins K.J., Tufte J., Yurk R.A., Ojha N.,
673 Afzal M. (2021b) For the COVID-19 Knowledge Accelerator (COKA) Initiative.
674 Scientific Evidence Code System Development Protocol. Created November 16,
675 2021. Last revised December 8, 2021. Available at:

676 [https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ld](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ldw0nD1g0)
677 [w0nD1g0](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pzGLdyVCKcu3s2gfSfPpXDQLIQsFnLZR14ldw0nD1g0).

678 Boutron I., Page M.J., Higgins J.P.T., Altman D.G., Lundh A., Hróbjartsson A. (2022)
679 Chapter 7: Considering bias and conflicts of interest among the included studies. In:
680 Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA
681 (editors). Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions version 6.3
682 (updated February 2022). Cochrane, 2022. Available from
683 www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.

684 Cochrane Collaboration. (2005) Glossary of Terms in The Cochrane Collaboration, Version
685 4.2.5 <http://aaz.hr/resources/pages/57/7.%20Cochrane%20glossary.pdf>.

686 Cooper G.S., Lunn R.M., Ågerstrand M., Glenn B.S., Kraft A.D., Luke A.M., Ratcliffe J.M.
687 (2016) Study sensitivity: Evaluating the ability to detect effects in systematic reviews
688 of chemical exposures. *Environ Int* 92-93:605-10. DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2016.03.017.

689 Dalkey N., Helmer O. (1963) An Experimental Application of the DELPHI Method to the Use
690 of Experts. *Management Science* 9:458-467. DOI: 10.1287/mnsc.9.3.458.

691 Dent M., Amaral R.T., Da Silva P., Amores, Ansell J., Boisleve F., Hatao M., Hirose A.,
692 Kasai Y., Kern P., Kreiling R., Milstein S., Montemayor B., Oliveira J., Richarz A.,
693 Taalman R., Vaillancourt E., Verma R., Posada N.V.O.R.C., Weiss C., Kojima H.
694 (2018) Principles underpinning the use of new methodologies in the risk assessment
695 of cosmetic ingredients. *Computational Toxicology* 7:20-26. DOI:
696 10.1016/j.comtox.2018.06.001.

697 Dirven H., Vist G.E., Bandhakavi S., Mehta J., Fitch S.E., Pound P., Ram R., Kincaid B.,
698 Leenaars C.H.C., Chen M., Wright R.A., Tsaïoun K. (2021) Performance of
699 preclinical models in predicting drug-induced liver injury in humans: a systematic
700 review. *Scientific Reports* 11:6403. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-85708-2.

701 ECHA. (2016) New approach methodologies in regulatory science : proceedings of a
702 scientific workshop : Helsinki, 19-20 April 2016, European Chemicals Agency,
703 [https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21838212/scientific_ws_proceedings_en.p](https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21838212/scientific_ws_proceedings_en.pdf/a2087434-0407-4705-9057-95d9c2c2cc57)
704 [df/a2087434-0407-4705-9057-95d9c2c2cc57](https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21838212/scientific_ws_proceedings_en.pdf/a2087434-0407-4705-9057-95d9c2c2cc57).

705 ECHA. (2023) In vitro methods, European Chemicals Agency,
706 [https://echa.europa.eu/support/registration/how-to-avoid-unnecessary-testing-on-](https://echa.europa.eu/support/registration/how-to-avoid-unnecessary-testing-on-animals/in-vitro-methods)
707 [animals/in-vitro-methods](https://echa.europa.eu/support/registration/how-to-avoid-unnecessary-testing-on-animals/in-vitro-methods).

708 EFSA, Tarazona J., Kass G., Dorne J.-L., Liem D., Paraskevopoulos K., Kleiner J., Heppner
709 C., Hugas M. (2022) Theme (Concept) Paper - New Approach Methodologies. EFSA
710 Supporting Publications 19:E200502E. DOI: 10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.e200502.

711 Eick S.M., Goin D.E., Chartres N., Lam J., Woodruff T.J. (2020) Assessing risk of bias in
712 human environmental epidemiology studies using three tools: different conclusions
713 from different tools. *Syst Rev* 9:249. DOI: 10.1186/s13643-020-01490-8.

714 EPA. (2018) Strategic plan to promote the development and implementation of alternative
715 test methods within the TSCA program. U.S. Environmental protection agency. EPA-
716 740-R1-8004, United States Environmental Protection Agency,
717 [https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2018-06/documents/epa_alt_strat_plan_6-20-
718 18_clean_final.pdf](https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2018-06/documents/epa_alt_strat_plan_6-20-18_clean_final.pdf).

719 EPA. (2022) ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments. U.S. EPA Office of
720 Research and Development, Washington, DC, EPA/600/R-22/268,
721 https://ordspub.epa.gov/ords/eims/eimscomm.getfile?p_download_id=545991.

722 EPA. (2023) Draft Protocol for Systematic Review in TSCA Risk Evaluations (assessed
723 10.02.2023), United States Environmental Protection Agency,
724 [https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-
725 systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations](https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations).

726 FEVIR Platform Version 0.80.0. (06.12.2022) Scientific Evidence Code System (SEVCO).
727 Computable Publishing®: CodeSystem Viewer,
728 <https://fevir.net/resources/CodeSystem/27270#SEVCO:00001>.

729 Frampton G., Whaley P., Bennett M., Bilotta G., Dorne J.-L.C.M., Eales J., James K., Kohl
730 C., Land M., Livoreil B., Makowski D., Muchiri E., Petrokofsky G., Randall N.,
731 Schofield K. (2022) Principles and framework for assessing the risk of bias for
732 studies included in comparative quantitative environmental systematic reviews.
733 *Environmental Evidence* 11:12. DOI: 10.1186/s13750-022-00264-0.

734 Gilmour N., Kern P.S., Alépée N., Boislève F., Bury D., Clouet E., Hirota M., Hoffmann S.,
735 Kühnl J., Lalko J.F., Mewes K., Miyazawa M., Nishida H., Osmani A., Petersohn D.,
736 Sekine S., van Vliet E., Klaric M. (2020) Development of a next generation risk
737 assessment framework for the evaluation of skin sensitisation of cosmetic
738 ingredients. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 116:104721. DOI:
739 10.1016/j.yrtph.2020.104721.

740 Krueger R.A., Casey M.A., Donner J., Kirsch S., Maack J.N. (2001) Designing and
741 Conducting Focus Group Interviews, *Social Development Papers* 31. Social Analysis:
742 Selected Tools and Techniques, Washington, D.C: World Bank,
743 http://web.worldbank.org/archive/website01028/WEB/IMAGES/SDP_36.PDF.

744 Momen N.C., Streicher K.N., da Silva D.T.C., Descatha A., Frings-Dresen M.H.W., Gagliardi
745 D., Godderis L., Loney T., Mandrioli D., Modenese A., Morgan R.L., Pachito D.,
746 Scheepers P.T.J., Sgargi D., Paulo M.S., Schlünssen V., Sembajwe G., Sørensen K.,
747 Teixeira L.R., Tenkate T., Pega F. (2022) Assessor burden, inter-rater agreement

748 and user experience of the RoB-SPEO tool for assessing risk of bias in studies
749 estimating prevalence of exposure to occupational risk factors: An analysis from the
750 WHO/ILO Joint Estimates of the Work-related Burden of Disease and Injury.
751 Environment International 158:107005. DOI:
752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.107005>.

753 NTP OHAT. (2015) Protocol to evaluate the evidence for an association between
754 perfluorooctanic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) exposure and
755 immunotoxicity, Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT), Division of the
756 National Toxicology Program, National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
757 https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/pfoa_pfos/protocol_201506_508.pdf. pp. 65-70.

758 NTP OHAT. (2019) Handbook for Conducting a Literature Based Health Assessment Using
759 OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration, Office of Health
760 Assessment and Translation (OHAT), Division of the National Toxicology Program,
761 National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences,
762 https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/ohat/pubs/handbookmarch2019_508.pdf.

763 PARC. (2023) PARC_What we do_Thematic areas_News_Events_Scientific publications
764 (assessed 11.05.2023), <https://www.eu-parc.eu/#news-and-events>.

765 Roth N., Zilliacus J., Beronius A. (2021) Development of the SciRAP Approach for
766 Evaluating the Reliability and Relevance of in vitro Toxicity Data. Frontiers in
767 Toxicology 3:746430. DOI: 10.3389/ftox.2021.746430.

768 Savović J., Jones H.E., Altman D.G., Harris R.J., Jüni P., Pildal J., Als-Nielsen B., Balk E.M.,
769 Gluud C., Gluud L.L., Ioannidis J.P., Schulz K.F., Beynon R., Welton N.J., Wood L.,
770 Moher D., Deeks J.J., Sterne J.A. (2012) Influence of reported study design
771 characteristics on intervention effect estimates from randomized, controlled trials.
772 Ann Intern Med 157:429-38. DOI: 10.7326/0003-4819-157-6-201209180-00537.

773 Sterne J.A.C., Hernán M.A., Reeves B.C., Savović J., Berkman N.D., Viswanathan M.,
774 Henry D., Altman D.G., Ansari M.T., Boutron I., Carpenter J.R., Chan A.-W., Churchill
775 R., Deeks J.J., Hróbjartsson A., Kirkham J., Jüni P., Loke Y.K., Pigott T.D., Ramsay
776 C.R., Regidor D., Rothstein H.R., Sandhu L., Santaguida P.L., Schünemann H.J.,
777 Shea B., Shrier I., Tugwell P., Turner L., Valentine J.C., Waddington H., Waters E.,
778 Wells G.A., Whiting P.F., Higgins J.P.T. (2016) ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of
779 bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. BMJ 355:i4919. DOI:
780 10.1136/bmj.i4919.

781 Sterne J.A.C., Page M.J., Savović J., Elbers R.G., Blencowe N.S., Boutron I., Cates C.J.,
782 Cheng H.-Y., Corbett M.S., Eldridge S.M., Hernán M.A., Hopewell S., Hróbjartsson
783 A., Junqueira D.R., Jüni P., Kirkham J.J., Lasserson T., Li T., McAleenan A., Reeves
784 B.C., Shepperd S., Shrier I., Stewart L.A., Tilling K., White I.R., Whiting P.F., Higgins

785 J.P.T. (2019) RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials.
786 British Medical Journal 366:14898. DOI: 10.1136/bmj.l4898

787 Tran L., Tam D.N.H., Elshafay A., Dang T., Hirayama K., Huy N.T. (2021) Quality
788 assessment tools used in systematic reviews of in vitro studies: A systematic review.
789 BMC Medical Research Methodology 21:101. DOI: 10.1186/s12874-021-01295-w.

790 Verhagen A.P., de Vet H.C., de Bie R.A., Kessels A.G., Boers M., Bouter L.M., Knipschild
791 P.G. (1998) The Delphi list: a criteria list for quality assessment of randomized
792 clinical trials for conducting systematic reviews developed by Delphi consensus. J
793 Clin Epidemiol 51:1235-41. DOI: 10.1016/s0895-4356(98)00131-0.

794 VKM. (2023) The Norwegian Scientific Committee of Food and Environment (VKM)
795 participates in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
796 (PARC) (assessed 11.05.2023),
797 [https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromche](https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromchemicals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html)
798 [micals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html](https://vkm.no/english/parc/parceuropeanpartnershipfortheassessmentofrisksfromchemicals.4.7205492a1864a8c8da2dcfd9.html).

799 Whaley P., Hooijmans C.R., Wattam S. (in preparation) Literature-based discovery of
800 assessment criteria for in vitro studies: a method and item bank.

801 Whiting P.F., Wolff R., Mallett S., Simera I., Savović J. (2017) A proposed framework for
802 developing quality assessment tools. Systematic Reviews 6:204. DOI:
803 10.1186/s13643-017-0604-6.

804